

Death as Viewed in Different World Religions and Particularly in Jainism in the Light of the Ritual of Death

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Death is the most curious phenomenon in the modern era. Persons living in the scientific and secularized society regard death with some ambivalence that has traditionally characterized towards God. The question of death give rise to variety of philosophical questions. One of the most important of these questions is about the nature of death¹. Generally, philosophers interpret this as a call for the analysis of the definition of the concept of death. Like Plato proposes to define death as a separation of soul from the body. Other have defined death simply as cessation of life. This too is problematic since an organism that goes into suspended animation ceases to live, but may not actually die.

The Judeo-Christian tradition mythically explains the death is the result of transgressions of a divine decree. Sometimes, death is attributed to an accident, such as the message that fails among some African cultures. In ancient Jewish religion, God gives life and takes it with death the punishment for sin.

Within the context of classical Hinduism, it is possible to find two responses of death: ritual and renunciation of the world. The ritual response to death involves a funeral procession by the chief mourner. With the exception of burying children and women dying during the child birth. A second response to death is renunciation of the world, a means for transcending the world by a symbolic death. The rationale is following: if one is already dead, one cannot die again. Within the teachings of the Buddha, death is directly connected with his

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First Noble Truth: all life is suffering. So, death is described as ‘mysterious’ because we cannot formulate a satisfactory concept of death. Death is typically regarded as a great evil, especially if it strikes someone too soon.

Thus, death is identified by terms like *marana*, *Vigama*, *Vinasa*, etc. It is identified with a process, in which the matter (*pudgala*), called *anubhuyamana*, would separate from the soul (*atman*), and then perish.² The Agamas preach that the loss of life (*jiva*) of body (*sarira*), by itself would not complete the process of death; it is the successful destruction of *ayu-karma*. The liberation is identified with terms such as *udurtana* (promoting oneself from the lowest stage, or hell), *kala* (escaping from the ordinary world of men) and *cyuta* (getting released from the world of demigods). The terms *udurtana* and *cyuta*, however, are reserved for divine beings.³ Some texts debate the *akala*, untimely or premature, and *svakala*, mature or timely, death. It is stated that death can be hastened through the *udirna* process, as a raw mango can be ripened by the *payala* and other processes of treatment.⁴

The *Tattvārtha Sūtra*, represents the earliest known compendium of Jain doctrinal beliefs. The author of this massive work was the chief disciple of Lord Mahavīra, a man named Umāsavāti, who created a “handbook for understanding the meaning of the basic truths”⁵ in which he describes fourteen stages through which a soul must travel in reach the end point of *moksa* or liberation upon death. These fourteen phases are known as the *Gunasthana* or “levels of virtue” and are likened in the rungs of a ladder.⁶

One may climb up or down on the ladder depending on their actions but in order to achieve the ultimate goal of transcending the cycle of *samsara*, a *jiva* must at some point move sequentially up the ladder, through the fourteen stages. Each higher stage moves the practitioner from various states of ignorance, passion, bad conduct, and more *karma* to states of omniscience, less passion, perfect conduct, and decreasing amounts of *karma* until there is no *karma* left at all. This path to perfection is sometimes called the “path of purification.”⁷

The Jains identify ritual-death with various terms, each term connoting a distinctive characteristic of its own.⁸ The wise, partially-wise, and foolish deaths are associated with aspirants who are respectively proficient, partially-proficient and foolish ones. The result of such deaths is recognized by the state of their attainment (such as *kevali*, *siddha*, etc.) in different heavens, and also from possibility and non-possibility of the recurrence of birth.⁹ The goal of the proficient one is to become *svayambhuor paramatma*, to achieve liberation of the

soul from *samsara* through Right Faith, Right Knowledge and Right Conduct. If Right Faith makes him realize the essential purity of the soul, Right knowledge leads him to understand the objective as laid down in the *Agamas* by the *Arhantas*: Right Conduct secures him perfect equanimity, in as much as he burns through penance, the *karma* accumulated over many existences.

In texts we find as many as forty-eight types of deaths, though all these falls under a couple of groupings. More succinct and meaningful lists are provided in the *Bhagavati Sutra* and *Bhagavati Aradhana*.¹⁰

After discussing different types of death, here it is important to bring into limelight the Jain ritual of death known as *Sallekhana* which is not found in any other religions of the world. Now the question is what is *Sallekhana*, to answer this we have to deal with the inner meaning of the term.

The derivation *sat* (praiseworthy), *lekhana* (emasculating or enervation of the body), or a praise worthy process of emasculating the body, appears to have been at the root of the ritual meaning of *sallekhana*.¹¹ The householder is expected to generally observe it at the last moment of his life (*maranantikamsallekhanamjosita*), to ensure a passionless, peaceful, unpressurised end.¹² Kundakundacarya regards *sallekhana* as part of the *siksavratas*, the vows which insure and promote renunciation.¹³ Kartikeya, Samantabhadra and Umasvati go into the nature of *sallekhana* after a discussion of the *silavratas*; this is also endorsed by Hemachandra and others.¹⁴ While Kundakunda treats *sallekhana* as one of the *vratas*, others give it a place in the context of ritual death.¹⁵

In the *Sthānānga Vrtti*, the *Acarya* Abhyayadevasuri said that *Sallekhana* is, “The activity by which the body is weakened and passions are overcome.”¹⁶ Other works give a slightly different linguistic allusion describing *Sallekhana* as the “peeling off of the passions” of the body and the forfeiture of bodily strength in order to strengthen the spirit.¹⁷ To weaken the physical body is *Dravya Sallekhana*, while to overcome the passions of the body is *Bhava Sallekhana*. Since Jain thought considers the body a prison for the soul, and the passions like the chains that hold the soul in its prison, it is of paramount importance in Jain belief in weaken these two entities in order to liberate the soul.

Sallekhana is a continuing practice aimed at weakening the body externally and the passions internally. Thus, *Sallekhana* can actually be an open-ended form of preparatory

penance that trains the aspirant to embrace the final act of death but does not necessarily have to end in death itself. The penance in and of itself is a spiritually rewarding ritual. The positive death that results from the *Sallekhana* is then called *Santhara* or *Samadhimarana*. The fact that the preparatory act of *Sallekhana* is designed to end in the death of the aspirant is qualified in the texts by the adjective “*maranantiki*” or “ending in death”. This adjective thus sets it apart linguistically and conceptually from *Santhara* which is essentially just death. Also, the option of specific periods of time in which to take *Sallekhana*, such as twelve years, twelve months or twelve weeks proves that it is an open-ended penance that is not always meant to end in death.

The term *Sallekhana* is used to encompass the preparatory penance preceding the enlightened death and *Samadhimarana* is the act of dying an enlightened death. A third term, *Santhara*, connotes the level of rigor of the final stages of dying. This process begins with the gradual withdrawal from all obsessions connected with the family as well as society, after realization of the true nature of worldly life; it is accompanied by repentance for the sins which originate from the brutal and boastful behaviour of the aspirant.¹⁸ Without understanding the true nature of piety (*dharma*) from the learned sages,¹⁹ the aspirant should not attempt to seek renunciation and initiation. A king may abandon his kingdom only after selecting his successor, training him in his duties, and familiarizing his successor with the responsibilities of his office and subjects. Even a sage-to-be has a duty to society, and without fulfilling it, he was not to attempt ascetic abandonment.

Whether a house-holder or a monk, he was required to ensure the stability of his monastery. Withdrawal from the family is followed by initiation into the realm of renunciators, by a *diksaguru*. The initiation is not a formal ceremony, a mechanical fulfilment of rites and rituals; it is an intense exercise to gain will-power. It begins with self-examination and proceeds to contemplate on the tenets which unravel the purpose and goal of life. It is a process of churning out the truth. No teacher is to initiate the aspirant without assuring himself of the intention, sincerity, and ability of the aspirant.²⁰

Almost all the texts lay down the conditions under which a monk or a lay-disciple is expected to seek termination of life by accepting the vow of *sallekhana*. A caution is given to all those who see only the purposelessness of the body; they are informed to note that the normal body has its own utility, and wanton destruction of it is not desirable. “When the body is still fit”, says the author of the *Yasastilaka Campu*, “do not attempt to destroy it; nor lament over that which gets naturally destroyed”,²¹ Asadhara makes a distinction between the

recoverable and terminal stages of life and advises destruction of only the last, through the process of renunciation and mortification.²²

The body has a role to play in helping the aspirant attain the three jewels (*ratnatraya*); hence, its destruction should not be the sole goal of an enlightened aspirant.²³ Nonetheless, the aspirant should know its limited use, its inevitable destruction, and its remote relevance to the ultimate welfare of the soul. “Birth, death, diseases are all associated with the body, not with me, (the soul), realizing this, I (soul) should cultivate detachment from the body”.²⁴

While death is to be hastened at the closing part of the life-span, preparation for this final act must be made throughout the life-time. During the preparatory period, prescribed vows (*nompis*) are to be observed; one such vow, named *acamlavardhana*, involving alternate days of fasting, engages the aspirant for as long a period as about fifteen years.²⁵ This means that the acceptance of the vow of *sallekhana* at the end of the life-span is not to be a spontaneous and sudden decision, but it is to be the culminating point of a series of severe austerities already suffered and mastered by the aspirant. This process is appropriately compared to a period of training which a warrior has to go through in order to be a successful fighter. If his training is incomplete and unsatisfactory, he would not be able to face a fierce enemy; if he happens to be one of those whose training (observance of *nompis*) has been thorough and perfect, but who would panic in the battlefield (while observing the *sallekhana*-vow), defeat and humiliation are bound to be his only gains.²⁶

Thus, the *sallekhana*-death is to be the proper fruit of rigorous penances practiced throughout one's life-time rather than as only an act to gain the final fruit.²⁷ *Two Stages in the Vow of Sallekhana*: The ritual of *sallekhana* falls into two parts –(1) *bahya-sallekhana*, relating to the external observances: (2) *abhyantara-sallekhana*, governing the internal purifications.²⁸ The external penances are aimed at subjugating the urges of the body, through a process of self-flagellation. The target of this penance is the subjugation of emotions (*ragas*); the weapon of attack is fasting.²⁹ The external austerities are spelt out in terms of a variety of constraints imposed on the intake of four types of food: consuming less than what is needed, conditional acceptance of food, rejection of any one or all of the nutrients such as ghee, milk, curd, sugar, salt, oil, etc. While practicing these, the art of mortifying the body without allowing the will-power to flag.³⁰ This process of flagellation of the body, in order to gain control over emotions (*ragas*), or passions (*kasayas*), is called *dravya-sallekhana*.³¹

The internal austerities (*abhyantara*) consist of expedition, reverence, service, study of the scriptures, concentration of mind, etc.³² This process by which the soul is cleansed of anger and longing, hatred and passion, fear and misery,³³ is identified as *bhava-sallekhana*.³⁴ Abandoning love, hatred, compassion, etc., and purifying the mind, the one who aspires for the *sallekhana* death should forgive others and forgive himself; he should begin pleasing words to be forgiven by his people and servants for the possible wrongs he may have committed in the past. As this is intended to free himself from *raga* and *dvesa*, (love and hatred), it may be regarded as an attempt to secure *kasaya-sallekhana*.³⁵

Gradually reducing and ultimately renouncing solid food, the aspirant should resort to nutritive liquids and, then, after some time, rejecting even the latter, take only warm water. In the next stage, he should abandon even the warm water, and fast rigorously; exerting to the best of his ability, he should concentrate on the *pancanamaskara* hymns until he breathes his last.³⁶

The final exertion should be devoid of *sallekhana-aticaras*, i. e. desire either to live or die, recollection of past friends and anticipation of sensual compensation in the next world for the ascetic sufferings in the present.³⁷ He who quenches his thirst from the nectar of *sallekhana* shall not only obtain the great comforts enjoyed by Lord Indra, but shall sail in the vast ocean of moksha. This state of moksha is marked by a synthesis of universal knowledge or *vidya*, *darsana*, *virya*, health, contentment, bliss and highest purity, which shine in him eternally like a diadem on the forehead of the lord of three-worlds. If he were to rebirth, he shall be born with all the best that humans should need on this earth, including the opportunity to observe the rite of *sallekhana*.³⁸ The ritual of *sallekhana* has been extensively discussed in the *kavya*-literature produced between the 9th and 14th centuries in Karnataka.

The *sallekhana*-vow was invariably administered by a learned and senior monk; the initiation of the aspirant took place in the presence of members of the monastic order, an assembly of prominent laity, and, on some occasions, with the chieftain or the ruler of the place (especially if he was a Jaina) participating in it. The aspirant was required to announce his intention to take the vow and prove the sincerity of his conviction to the congregation; it was after ascertaining the causes of the action and the capacity of the aspirant to endure the severity of the ensuing observances, that his faith in the pursuit was accepted, and he was helped to fulfil the vows. *Srtamuni*, who lived in Sravana Belgola,³⁹ was more fortunate than Manika Sena, who lived at Hadurvalli,⁴⁰ because the former could seek the guidance and help of the order, while the latter had to depend more on the secular chieftain than on the weakly organized order for fulfilling his *sallekhana*-vow. Though both accepted death in the 15th century, the

strong religious base at Sravana Belgola and the absence of such a base at Haduvalli, perhaps made this difference inevitable.

The *sallekhana*-vow seems to have been observed over a period of anywhere between two-and-a-half months and three-days before the termination of life. Mallisena's observance were concluded within three days; Srinandi and Bhaskaranandi took a month to complete the vow; Manika Sena had to observe the vow for thirty-three days, while Nemicandracarya took as many as two-and-a-half months to complete his vow.⁴¹

The peaceful death and the journey towards achieving it were perhaps developed as a response to the truth written in the *Dasavaikalika* Sutra which says ever so simply. "Everyone wants to live and none wants to die."⁴² In the broadest sense of Jain philosophy an eternal soul (*jiva*) is subject to the cycle of birth, death and rebirth (*samsara*). When in a physical form, particularly a human form the worth of the body that houses the soul is based on utility. The physical body is a tool or the conduit by which the soul seeks out knowledge and enlightenment and proceeds on its spiritual journey. When the physical body begins to fail and is more of a burden than an asset the Jain canons teach that the enlightened aspirant is best served by accepting that their body is but a temporary vessel and that death is a natural progression and thus it is preferable to embrace death rather than hang on to life.

The Jain canons in essence suggest that rather than allowing the grim spectator of death to stalk you, you as the aspirant, give up life-sustaining practices such as eating and drinking and meet death with a posture of openness. This psychological acceptance of death you adopt a position or attitude of equanimity towards death. This process of accepting death, of psychologically preparing oneself to voluntarily end one's life, known as *Sallekhana*, should ideally result in the person looking back on a life of piety and therefore having no fear because they are assured of a good reincarnation.

The *Tattvārthasūtra* tells that the aspirant should think, "I have followed the path of virtue and thus I do not fear death."⁴³ Conversely one who has lived a sinful life full of worldly attachments dies fretfully, fearing death for fear of being reborn in hellish circumstances or as an animal.

The Jain emphasis on the primary importance of conduct in achieving spiritual liberation has led to the development of a highly rigorous code of monastic practices and a very stringent code of conduct for its laity. Severe penance as a means of purging accumulated *karma* from the soul is prescribed for all followers of the Jain philosophy.

Here I want to bring into limelight that *Samādhimarana* and *Sallekhana* are frequently used interchangeable terms, both in the media and conversationally, in the literature they have distinctly different grammatical and conceptual nuances. *Samādhimarana* is a state of being, a peaceful death and a dispassionate end. It is the experience of death itself, a singular point in time. *Sallekhana* is a vow followed by an elaborate process; a ritualistic journey one embarks on to achieve *Samadhimarana*.⁴⁴

At this juncture I must conclude by raising a question: what makes the Jain form of death different from the death followed in other religions of the world? The answer certainly will be- the Jain form of death gives an idea of exclusive death- it is the fine art of dying gracefully and with dignity.

A Jain may embark on the ultimate renunciation of his /her life by preparing for a cheerful, stoic and positive outlook on death after having sought all forgiveness and made every attempt to detach himself from all attachment of life like affection, grief, fear etc., in order to ensure a permanent ending from the eternal and unchanging life cycle of Karma. This is how Jain way of death differs from other religions of the world.

References

1. Robert F. Weir, *Ethical issues in Death and Dying*, New York Columbia University Press, 1977.
2. *Bha. Ara.*, 25. See the commentary in Sanskrit by *Aparajitasuri*.
3. *Dhavalā* 6-1, 7-1, 76-243, 477-22: cited in the *JainendraSiddhantakosa*, III. P.293.
4. *Rajavartika*, 2-53, 10, 158-8; cited in the *JainendraSiddhantakasa*, III, p. 296.
5. Glasenapp, *Jainism: An Indian Religion of Salvation*, p.126.
6. Jaini, *The Jaina Path of Purification*. P. 141.
7. *Ibid.* p. 141
8. *Acarasara*, X; *Sa. Dharma.*, VIII; *Ratna. Srav.*, 112-150; *Aca. Su.*, 1.7.8-7 to 23; *Bha. Ara.*, from v. 64 onwards. The most elaborate account on the subject, given by Sivakotyacarya in the last of these works, forms the basis of our study.

9. *Pravacanasara*, I; *Paramatma-yoga*, pp 9 ff; *Tattva.Su.*, IV in particular. Cf., Sogani EDJ., pp.237 ff. See also. “The Concept of the Deity”. By Malvania, D.D., In a *Aspects of Jaina Art and Architecture*, ed. By Shah, U.P., AND Dhaky, M.A., (Ahmedabad, 1975), p.4.
10. The *Bha. Su.* Identifies two main categories: *bala-marana* and *pandita-marana* (2, 1, 91) and lists the following twelve kinds under the *bala-marana*- (1) *valatah-marana* (loss of self-control, subject to senses, starvation); (2) *vasartta-marana* (tonnenting senses, overpowered by sensuous objects) (3) *antahsalya-marana* (allowing foreign material such as thorn-pikes etc., in the body, or allowing passions to develop); (4) *tadbhava-marana* (fall from mountain top); (7) *jalapravesa – marana*(drowning); (8) *jvalana-marana* (entering into fire); (9) *Visabhaksana-marana* (gulping poison); (10) *sastravapata-marana* (killing oneself with a weapon); (11) *vehayasa-marana* (hanging from a tree); (12) *grddhaprsta-marana*(attacked by vultures, wild animals or sharp weapons). Under the *pandita-marana* it refers only to two kinds – (1) *padopagamana-marana* (firmly planted like a tree until death) and (2) *bhaktapratyakhyana-marana* (refusing food and drinks). Studies in the *Bhagawati sutra*, Sikdar, J. C., pp. 264 ff).
11. *Ratna. Sra.*, see commentary on 122, p. 517.
12. Acarya Umaswati, *Tattvarthadhigamasutra*, (SBJ, No II), ed, by Jaini, J.L., (Arrah, 1920), VII,22, p. 145
13. *Cartitra Pahuda* 25. 26-Cited by Sogani, K.C. EDJ., p. 91.
14. *Ratna. Sra.*, 92. 93; *Saga Dharma*, V, 25, 26; *Kartti.*, 368. Cited by Sogani, *Ibid*, p.93.
15. *Pu. Pu.*, p. 145.
16. “*Samlikhyatenayasarira-kasayadiiti Samlekhanam*” – *Sthananga 2, Uddesaka 2 Vrtti*
17. “*Samlekhanam dravyatah sarirasthabhavatah kasayanam krastapadanam samlekha-samlekhaneti*” – *Vrhadvrtti*
18. Bandhuvarma, *Hari.*, X, *vacana* after v. 9, p. 211.
19. Nagavarma, *Va. Pu.*, VII, *vacana* after v. 35, p. 119.
20. Bandhuvanna, *Hari.*, X, *vacana* after v. 13, *Acanna, Va. Pu.*, XII, after, p. 199.
21. *Yasastilaka-Campa*, VI, 860; cf.’ *Sravakacara-Samgraha*, pt. III, ed. By Hiralai Sastri, (Sholapur, 1977).
22. Asadhara, *Saga. Dharma.*, VIII, 6; *Sra. Sam.*’ pt. III.

23. Asadhara, *op. cit.*, VIII, 5.
24. Sakalakirti, *op. cit.*, XXII, 13.
25. Santinatha, *Su. Ca.*, IX 5-14, pp. 148 ff. refers to this vow, which lasted for fourteen Years, seven months and five days.
26. Ayatavarma cited in Ratna. Sra., p.519, n. 1; Sakalakirti, Prasanottara-Sravakacara, XXII, 17; *Yasastilaka Campu*, VI, 866.
27. It is appropriately described as *antakriyakaranam-tapah-phalam-Ratna. Sra.*, 123, Cf., Sri *Kundakunda-Sravakacara*, XII, 4.
28. *Bha. Ara.*, 208
29. Sakalakiru's *Prasnottara-Sravakacara*, XXII, 30-33.
30. *Tattva. Su.*, IX, 20.
31. *JKS.*, 383: Cf., *Pancastikaya*, 173, 253, *Bha. Ara.*, 208-272.
32. *Tattva. Su.*, IX, 20.
33. Medhavi, *Dharmasamgraha*, VII, 31; *Sra. Sam.*, II, p. 180.
34. *JKS.*, p. 383; cf., *Pancastikaya*, 173, 253, *Bha. Ara.*, 208-272.
35. *JKS.*, p.383; *Bha. Ara.*, 208-272; Umasvami, *Sravakacara*, 453;
36. Padmanandi, *Sravakacara –Saroddhara*, 252-356.
37. *Bha. Ara.*, 248-50.
38. Settar, S. *Pursuing Death*, p.191.
39. *EC II*, SB 364.
40. *KI I*, 49.
41. *EC II*, SB 77, *SII XX*, 52; *EC V*, (NE), Kn. 35.
42. “*Savvejiva vi icehantijiviumnamarijjiurh*” – *Dasavaikalika*, 6.10.
43. “*Maranantikim Sallekhanam josita*”- *Tattvarthasutra*, 7.22
44. Baya, *Death with Equanimity : The Pursuit of Immortality*, P. 43.